

> DESIRE6G <

D6.1: Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan (CODP)

HEU 6G SNS JU Project

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the communication and dissemination plan of DESIRE6G. Under each part of the plan, we present the list of activities, as well as the targeted metrics. Standardization deserves substantial attention in this document, in which the initial standardization roadmap is introduced, including the identification of relevant standard development organizations and relevant open-source projects. Early achievements in some of the activities are also listed.

Keywords

Communication, dissemination, standardization.

Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electronics and Electrical Engineering
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
ITU-T	International Telecommunications Union – Telecommunications standardization sector
NMRG	Network Management Research Group
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
ONOS	Open Network Operating System
OPNFV	Open Platform for NFV
O-RAN	Operator Defined Next Generation RAN
OSM	Open Source MANO
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SDO	Standard Development Organization
TSG	Technical Specification Groups
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

The main contributions of this document are:

- Presentation of the communication and dissemination plan.
- Presentation of the early achievements (first 6 months of the project, from January to June 2023) according to this plan.

Communication includes all the activities related with the promotion of the project and its results beyond the projects own community. This includes explaining DESIRE6G research in a way that is understood by the non-specialist, e.g., the media and the public. Dissemination includes activities related with raising awareness of the project's results towards the technical community working in the same research field. In general, this will be done through scientific publications, and participation and organization of technical and scientific events. Although standardization belongs to exploitation, this deliverable also covers standardization, as it is not as sensitive to partners as exploitation and it is important to report on plans and early achievements.

The communication and dissemination plan (see Figure 1 for a complete scheme) started at the proposal stage with the non-disclosure agreement (NDA) signature and the identification of the various components of the project that could have an impact from a research point of view. Once the grant was awarded, the grant preparation phase, through the consortium agreement, served to define governance rules, including innovation management, and establishment of access rights, among others.

After that, and from project start, the plan is structured in various phases.

During the *Raise Awareness* phase, at the initial stages of the project, the focus is on communication (e.g., setting up the web portal and social media accounts and high-level project presentations) to make the project known not just to the technical community but to a larger audience outside the project topics including the public. Dissemination and standardization activities also start in this phase with preliminary technical ideas.

In the *Presentation of Results* phase, dissemination and exploitation activities increase their intensity since the architecture and integration efforts will have produced meaningful results. Initial

demonstrations of specific concepts of the architecture are also expected during this phase. However, it is in the *Integrated Technical Demonstration* phase where demonstration activities involving multiple blocks of the architecture working in an integrated way are expected.

Finally, in the *Long-lasting Impact* phase the projects generates an impact to other research or exploitation actions taken once the project is finished. This includes shaping the topics and framework of future research projects, exploiting DESIRE6G concepts in a market-oriented way by incorporating them in products and services, and leaving the DESIRE6G footprint in standards that include project contributions.

The plan not only defines the various activities undertaken, but it also defines target metrics for each of them.

In accordance with the plan, some early results have already been produced. Some highlights follow:

- Communication
 - Design of promotion material, website, and creation of news, social media accounts, along with initial actions to raise awareness about the project through these means. This already resulted in more than 1600 visits to the website and an increasing impact through social media.
 - Communication talks and the preparation of a video (to be released during the second half of 2023) to present the scope of the project.
 - Some events organized targeting general public (e.g., high school students).
- Dissemination
 - 9 accepted publications, some of them joint with other projects.
 - 6 dissemination talks to explain DESIRE6G and its concepts to a technical audience.
- Standardization and Open Source
 - Identification of relevant SDOs for networking (e.g., 3GPP, IETF, ETSI) and monitoring of groups of interest for potential contribution.
 - Identification of relevant open-source projects for networking (e.g., Openstack, OSM).
 - Definition of the initial standardization roadmap according to the timelines of the SDOs and the project.

1. Introduction

The communication and dissemination plan of DESIRE6G includes the three following groups of activities as follows:

- **Communication:** It includes all the activities related with the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes communication of its research in a way that it is understood by non-specialist, e.g., the media and the public.
- **Dissemination:** It includes activities related with raising awareness of its results in a technical community working on the same research field. In general, this will be done through peer-reviewed publications in academic conferences and journals, and participation and organization of technical events.
- **Standardization and Open Source:** it covers monitoring and impact in standardization activities, and contributions to Open Source.

The communication and dissemination plan includes all phases of the project (i.e., proposal, grant preparation, project lifetime, and after the project ends), where the focus is on activities tailored to each period. A summary of the plan is presented in Figure 1.

The goal of the proposal stage was to lay down the foundations for all activities following in the project execution phases both in technical and legal terms. Technical challenges were identified at the proposal phase and corresponding research topics with potential to generate exploitation impact were selected for the project execution phases. The proposal stage also served to set the legal and organizational framework, including the signing of the NDA, the identification of responsibilities (e.g., communication manager), or the per-partner IPR management. All items included are listed in the upper part of the figure next to the label Proposal stage.

FIGURE 1: DESIRE6G COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Once the grant was awarded, the grant preparation phase involved the legal departments of the consortium members to specify the legal framework more clearly. Therefore, the consortium agreement served to define governance rules, including innovation management, IPR ownership rules, and establishment of access rights, among others. The complete list is provided in the figure next to label *Grant preparation stage*.

The communication and dissemination plan activities will gain momentum during the *project implementation* stage. Figure 1 presents the various project milestones and deliverables directly related with the implementation of the plan as well as the various activities and phases during project execution. All activities will be carried out in parallel, but the emphasis of each of them will be different depending on the phase of the project. During the *Raise Awareness* phase, at the initial stages of the project, the focus is on communication (e.g., setting up the web and social media and high-level project presentations) to make the project known not just to the R&D community but to a larger audience outside the project including the public. Dissemination and standardization activities also start in this phase with preliminary technical contributions. More specifically, all the activities below are initiated in this phase:

- Web portal and social media accounts.
- Project brochure.
- Project poster.
- High-level project presentation and participation at events to explain project scope.
- Videos.
- Participation in events for a general audience (e.g., open science week).
- University lectures in graduate, master and doctoral courses.

The above activities require more effort at the beginning of the project due to the preparation of the initial communication resources and framework needed throughout the project, but they continue until the end of the project and after the project ends. Some of these resources (e.g., brochure, poster and high-level presentation) are meant to be available for use in events where DESIRE6G targets general dissemination of the project mission.

In the *Presentation of Results* phase, dissemination and exploitation activities increase their intensity. Initial demonstrations are expected during this phase (e.g., at events such as Mobile World Congress or EUCNC). More specifically, these activities include:

- Dissemination
 - Publication of research results in technical journals and conferences.
 - Enrolment of PhD and Master students on the topics of the project.
 - Participation in public exhibitions and demonstrations.
 - Organization of special events (e.g., technical workshops).
 - Collaboration with other relevant projects.
- Standardization and Open Source
 - Contribution to relevant open-source software projects.
 - Contribution to standardization bodies according to the standardization plan initially presented in this deliverable and continually refined throughout the project lifetime.

Furthermore, it is in the Integrated *Technical Demonstration* phase where demonstration activities take more relevance and experimental results are obtained to validate the main architectural concepts of the project in an integrated way.

Finally, the project aims at having an impact after the project ends through other research projects, standardization contributions that include DESIRE6G concepts, or by influencing products and services of partner organizations. These activities conform the *Long-lasting Impact* phase.

In addition to the preparation of the communication material, the initial phase of the project posed substantial effort in defining the standardization plan that will be implemented during the project. This includes the identification of relevant SDOs and open-source projects, and the matching of project timelines with those of SDOs. Furthermore, this initial plan will be periodically updated to adapt to standardization interests and context variation.

In the same way, the whole communication and dissemination plan will be periodically updated throughout the project if, for instance, new activities need to be defined or new collaboration and dissemination opportunities appear. The following sections describe in detail the work plan for each of the activities. After that, the early achievements in some of the activities of the plan are also listed.

2. Communication plan

DESIRE6G will create, from the early stages of the project, a basic set of presentation materials targeted for various audience types; a communication package that will be used as the core communication measure to promote the project as summarized in the following section.

2.1 Work plan

The following table includes the targeted audience, the related activities, the timing, and the metrics of the communication activities, including quantified goals.

TABLE 1: COMMUNICATION PLAN

Audience	Activity	Timing	Metric
All, General public, Research	Project website. DESIRE6G will share its concepts, results and achievements through its dedicated project website. The website will be the primary tool of communication and promotion of the project.	M3 and cont. update	Number of unique visits, Most visited pages, Most downloaded papers
All, General public	Press releases, posters, leaflets. DESIRE6G will prepare and distribute project poster, press releases and leaflets to raise public awareness.	M3 and event-driven	1 leaflet and 1 poster available at Month 6. Published press releases (target: two per year)
General public	Public Communication. DESIRE6G project will regularly be promoted through participation and organization of events for society at large and distribution through social media. We will also make use of EC communication tools and magazines.	M1 and event-driven	Num. of events organized / attended (target: at least one per year) LinkedIn and Twitter metrics
General public, Interest groups	Videos. DESIRE6G will work on the creation of public videos to raise awareness and to advertise the proposed network scenarios and their capabilities	M7, M36 and event-driven	Explanatory video and of all demo activities available in the web
Students	Lecture materials related with DESIRE6G will be introduced in academic courses taught by	Pot. every 6 months	Num. of courses related with project topics

partners		
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3. Dissemination plan

The purpose of the dissemination plan is to guarantee that all concepts and technologies developed in the DESIRE6G project are disseminated adequately to relevant entities, including standards development organizations. Dissemination and Collaboration (primarily within the SNS JU) activities are expected to be conducted in Year 1 to help promote the project concept and initial results to the large European and more International R&D community and raise opportunities for synergy with other projects and activities. This chapter presents first the plan set in Year 1 and reports next the related achievements for dissemination and collaboration activities respectively. The dissemination activities are carried out continuously when there is the appropriate combination of availability of project results and opportunity. In this respect, project milestones are a key source of dissemination. As far as dissemination is concerned, the following activities are expected:

Publications in selected journals and magazines, such as IEEE/ACM journals, transactions and magazines (e.g., IEEE JSAC, IEEE TNSM, IEEE Communications Magazine, IEEE Network) and reputed international conferences (e.g., IEEE ICC, IEEE Globecom, IEEE IM, ACM Conext). **Collaborations** with other EU and international research projects through SNS JU working groups, network2020, and other Horizon Europe projects in support of the SNS JU commitments and towards the realization of the 5G vision. **Presentations** and participation on behalf of the project in research-oriented workshops, industry-oriented workshops (e.g., ETSI workshops on standardization), technology platforms, and any other similar forum, including participation on academic and industrial panels organized in these events. Participation in **public exhibitions and demonstrations** for academia (e.g., demonstrations in conferences) and industry (e.g., Mobile World Congress, EUCNC, SDN and NFV World Congress or equivalent) to disseminate research work to create awareness of DESIRE6G technology and applications. **Organization of events**, such as workshops collocated with well-established conferences (e.g., IEEE ICC, IEEE Globecom, ACM Mobihoc) to showcase DESIRE6G results.

3.1 Dissemination work plan for reporting period 1

The dissemination activities will be steered towards generating impact through peer-reviewed publications, presentations, talks, demonstrations, panels, workshops, and events. The goals set in Reporting period 1 include¹:

- Submission of at least 15 scientific articles for publication at reputed conferences and journals on reporting period 1. The goal for the whole lifetime of the project is to have 30 published/accepted publications.
- Submission of at least 10 contributions to SDOs, such as 3GPP, IETF, ETSI, IEEE, ITU over the lifetime of the project.
- Submission of at least 8 commits to Open-Source projects/efforts over the lifetime of the project.
- Submission of at least 2 joint documents scientific / articles / publications for publication at reputed conferences and journals together with EU and international research projects, e.g., through SNS JU working groups, or working groups of other platforms, such as networld2020).
- 4 demonstrations of project related prototypes or solutions during the lifetime of the project.
- Organization of at least 2 research and 1 industry-oriented workshops during the lifetime of the project.
- Participation to 5 research- or industry-oriented events during the lifetime of the project.
- Editing of 2 special issues during the lifetime of the project.
- Addition of core skills for technology development within the project into academic curriculums, along with the proposal of PhD and MSc theses on specific topics on 5Growth research agenda.

¹ Note that some of the goals set in the Description of Action (DoA) can be easily split into the two reporting periods, while others tend to be done just in the last one (e.g., demonstrations). This is the reason that some goals are still referred to the whole lifetime of the project.

The following table summarizes the dissemination plan.

TABLE 2: DESIRE6G DISSEMINATION PLAN (REPORTING PERIOD 1)

Audience	Activity	Timing	Metric
Academic and industrial research	DESIRE6G aims at publishing its work in selected, high impact-factor journals and magazines on communications/networking (e.g., IEEE Communication Magazine, IEEE JSAC), and reputed international conferences (e.g., ICC, PIMRC, Globecom, CoNext, EUCNC) as well as smaller-scale but highly targeted. An appropriate balance between academic and industrial awareness will be sought.	Continuous	At least 15 publications per reporting period in top-tier scientific journals and conferences.
Other research projects	Collaboration with other EU and international research projects (e.g., through SNS JU working groups, or working groups of other platforms, such as networkd2020) will also be key towards a coordinated action inside the SNS JU and with other HEU projects related with topics addressed in the project	SNS JU WGs & ad hoc bi-lateral collaboration	Num. of meetings attended (target: at least two per year). Num. of joint documents generated (target: at least two per year).
Mostly academia, but also industry	Organization, presentations and participation in the organization of events (e.g., panels, targeted workshops, workshops co-located with relevant conferences, special sessions) and participation in these same kind of sessions as keynote speaker, panelist, etc., thanks to important vendors, technology providers and operators, high-tech SMEs, and reputed academic organizations within the consortium.	Particip. in one per yr. One workshop organized	Organization of one 30-people workshop co-located with a major conference (e.g., EUCNC, IEEE WCNC, ICC, INFOCOM) with 70% satisfaction in the workshop quality poll for attendees. Participation in workshops: we measure the number of events (target: at least one per year), we will measure the metrics (web access, cites) of work presented to measure its impact.
Industry	Exploitation workshop. Chaired by the innovation manager and specifically devoted to maximizing the exploitation outcomes of the project in terms of standardization, patenting/licensing, and products and	One workshop org. before M34	One 30-people exploitation workshop before the end of the project with 70% satisfaction in the poll for

	services. Experts on innovation from the various companies representing all industrial sectors already in the project (verticals, operators, vendors, and SMEs and external experts acting as advisors on maximizing the exploitation outcome of the project.		attendees.
Mostly industry, & also academia	Technology demonstration. The project team believes that the realization of proofs-of-concept is the key to maximize innovation potential. 5Growth will participate in demonstrations of key project components in exhibition booths in fairs, such as those of EUCNC, or industrial events, such as Mobile World Congress (MWC), where some of partners have regularly exhibited.	Approx. every 6 months	Technology demonstration in at least two events per reporting period. More demonstrations in several events are targeted.
Undergraduate, Master and PhD students	Dissemination in BSc, MSc and PhD courses of DESIRE6G related technology, including BSc, MSc and PhD thesis. Through academic partners, DESIRE6G aims at disseminating and training students on relevant DESIRE6G technologies.	Continuous	Num. of impacted courses and thesis supervised.

3.2 Synergies with other projects

In this section, we have identified a set of ongoing projects (at the time of publishing this deliverable) which results may impact DESIRE6G. For all the projects identified, there is an involved DESIRE6G partner, hence we can use the already established relation to maintain a cooperation between projects. Only a selection of projects is listed below. Many other projects that are not listed may as well impact the DESIRE6G design.

Project name	Short Description	Technical relationships	Contact
On-going EU/Horizon Europe projects			
PREDICT-6G	PREDICT-6G aims to create a secure, modular, interoperable, and extensible deterministic network and management framework that automates the definition, provisioning, monitoring, fulfillment, and life-cycle management of end-to-end deterministic services over multiple network domains. This will hide the complexity of continuously balancing and re-configuring the constituent domain specific enablers to maintain a consistent end-to-end determinism.	Complementary to the efforts in DESIRE6G towards supporting extreme URLLC requirements, PREDICT-6G aims at enabling deterministic behaviour in multi-domain multi-technology wireless networks.	UC3M, TID, UPC, ERI-HU
DETERMINISTIC6G	DETERMINISTIC6G addresses three central challenges of future deterministic end-to-end communication enabled by 6G: (i) a new architecture for 6G systems providing deterministic performance and secure integration of 6G systems and new edge computing solutions into deterministic communication contexts, e.g., TSN and DetNet; (ii) 6G system awareness enabled by novel data-driven approaches including novel deep neural network-based classifiers and regressors; (iii) leveraging novel digital twins of both 6G networks and cyber-physical systems, to anticipate situational circumstances impacting determinism of networks and safety of cyber-physical systems.	Deterministic6G is primarily interested in making the 6G system deterministic and secure integration of 6G systems into wireline deterministic communication technologies such that some key use cases are considered as guidelines to build successful business relations between the apps	ERI-HU, CNIT/SSSA

		and the network. Desire6G could utilize the use cases and the API work.	
Hexa-X-II	Hexa-X-II is the flagship project for the first definition of a 6G framework architecture. As such, it has the mandate of coordinating other SNS projects from Phase I towards the achievement of designing features relevant for 6G.	DESIRE6G is one of the Stream B SNS Phase 1 projects. As such it should be kept in touch with Hexa-X-II.	UC3M, TID, ERI-HU
ADROIT6G	ADROIT6G is an SNS JU project aiming at introducing distributed AI into 6G networks, which are expected to be programmable.	DESIRE6G focuses on programmability aspects of 6G networks, whereas ADROIT6G focuses on how to leverage that programmability and introduce distributed AI solutions. Initial bilateral engagements are in place ADROIT6G-DESIRE6G towards a joint workshop to identify synergies.	CNIT, NVIDIA
National Projects, Celtic program, and Internal projects			
CATRIN (NWO)	<i>The Controllable, Accountable, Transparent: The Responsible Internet</i> (CATRIN) projects allows users (e.g., providers of critical services)	Complementary to the work on In Band Telemetry	UVA

	<p>to request descriptions of the chains of network operators that handle their data flows, for instance in terms of their security and administrative properties and their interrelations (Transparency). Based on these details, users can request network operators to handle their data flows in a particular way, exploiting data plane programmability, for example by allowing them to only pass-through operators whose equipment and geolocations they have specified (Controllability). The Responsible Internet also allows users to verify whether operators act as they declared and to trace incidents and attacks to their root cause (Accountability).</p>	<p>envisioned for DESIRE6G. The outputs of the CATRIN project can influence and provide insights on service requirements in terms of trust and security.</p>	
6G-DATADRIVEN	<p>6G-DATADRIVEN is an Spanish project (2022-2024) that is committed to develop data-driven approaches by (i) designing and incorporating distributed AI/ML tools exploiting distributed data collection and processing within edge computing platforms; (ii) creating plug-and-play solutions to flexibly deploy and operate non-public 5G networks, building on the platforms developed in previous projects; (iii) developing secure data distribution schemes; (iv) implementing zero-touch, AI-based network and service management, fully meeting the specific needs of smart manufacturing and emergency support environments.</p>	<p>Some efforts in 6G-DATADRIVEN are complimentary to the URLLC support from DESIRE6G, namely those related to the implementation of zero-touch, AI-based network management.</p>	UC3M, TID

Furthermore, project partners will participate to multiple SNS JU working groups, which are currently being defined. Taking current 5G-PPP working groups as an example:

- Pre-Standardization
- Vision and Societal Challenges
- 5G Architecture

- Trials
- SME
- Software Networks
- Security
- Test, Measurements and KPI Validation

Their scope is described at: <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-work-groups/>. This participation will include presenting and representing the project in all periodic meetings that are organized and participation in joint actions (e.g., co-organization of events, joint documents/papers, joint demonstrations). The scope and actual working groups are currently being discussed and defined at the 6G-IA.

Additionally, the project will also participate in the SNS JU boards towards a tight coordination with the rest of SNS JU projects: the project coordinator in the steering board and the technical manager in the technology board.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the following are the 6G-IA proposed working groups, chaired by 6G-IA members (we underline those that are potentially relevant to DESIRE6G and that we plan to participate/contribute to):

- **Vision WG**, aiming at developing a vision for Smart Networks and Services beyond 2030.
- **Open SNS**, aiming at exploring open solutions for 5G and beyond 5G/6G networks.
- **Trials**, developing a European Trial Roadmap for beyond 5G/6G systems in the contexts of SNS.
- **Pre-standardization**, facilitating impact creation in particular towards relevant standardization bodies and open source.
- **5G/6G for Connected and Automated Mobility - R&I Stream**, aimed at establishing a knowledge base and facilitating the exchange of information on ongoing R&I activities in the field.
- **Spectrum WG**, focusing on the regulatory and technical aspects that relate to spectrum for beyond 5G and 6G systems.
- **Security WG**, fostering development of 5G/6G Security Community.

- **6G-IA SNS Forum WG**, proposed to serve as a forum for open technical discussions on any technological topics of interest.
- **WiTaR (Women in Telecommunications and Research) WG**, proposed to promote a gender-balanced approach in European R&I activities including industry and academia.

Additionally, the following is the list of SNS Projects WGs, chaired by SNS Projects members (we underline those that are potentially relevant to DESIRE6G and that we plan to participate/contribute to):

- **SNS Architecture WG**, with the goal of collecting, analyzing, and consolidating information from SNS projects on architecture research requirements and results (with a clear link to SNS Stream B).
- **SNS Reliable Software Networks WG**, aimed at analyzing how 6G networks will be designed as software enabled platforms and include topics related to AI/MAL, service provision/orchestration as well as security (DevSecOps) (with a clear link to SNS Stream B).
- **SNS Test Measurement and Validation WG**, bringing together SNS projects that have common interest in the development and progress of topics related to test and measurement methods, test cases, procedures, etc. The current proposal is that at least all Stream C and D projects should participate, as well as any other Stream A and B projects that are planning to provide at least a PoC or higher TRL solutions.
- **Communication technologies and Devices WG**, bringing together SNS projects working in the areas of wireless communications as well as communication infrastructure and devices. This WG will deal with topics related to 6G RAN enablers and solutions as well as optical communications, integration of NTN with 6G networks, short range communications and IoT evolution (with a clear link to SNS Stream B).

3.3 Open Science

DESIRE6G will follow thoroughly all the required actions to be aligned with the Open Science practices as they are defined in the Horizon Europe guidelines. In particular, the open science practices are supported by five pillars:

- **Early and open sharing of research.** During DESIRE6G project lifetime, all partners will follow methods that assure the early and open sharing of the project outcomes. More specifically, plans are shared in advance of implementation. This methodology enhances the research results as it addresses a point which is often underemphasized, that a research hypothesis can only be truly held before the data are looked at and usually before the data are collected.
- **Research output management and measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs.** DESIRE6G will pay attention to ensure reproducibility of outputs by covering the three research processes that reproducibility is based on: reproduction, replication, and re-use, which rest on the availability of data and methods from the original study.
- **Open access to research outputs and participation in open peer-review.** Open Access (OA) has been a core strategy by the European Commission to improve knowledge circulation and re-usability. All projects receiving Horizon funding are required to provide online access to any peer-reviewed scientific research article published in scholarly journals, free and reusable (Article 17 of the Model Grant Agreement). DESIRE6G fully embraces this vision.

DESIRE6G will leverage the services provided by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), which is an active service provider of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This European initiative, which lists 37+ million publications and 9+ million research data, has the mission to promote open scholarship and improve the discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility and monitoring of data-driven research results, across scientific disciplines.

A more detailed explanation on how DESIRE6G plan to manage open data and publications can be found in [1].

4. Standardization Plan

From its inception, DESIRE6G has a clear goal on contributing to both standardization and open-source activities. Such purpose is perceived as a bidirectional interaction between the project and external that external communities. In explain, any progress in standardization and open-source arena can influence the development of DESIRE6G architecture and innovations, but also the other way around, that is, any progress derived from the project execution advancing beyond of the state of the art can be contributed to the preponderant Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) and open-source (OS) projects in specific technological areas.

The DESIRE6G project counts with an important set of industrial and academic partners with relevant presence in both SDOs and open-source communities. This is the foreseen vehicle for facilitating the bidirectional interaction previously mentioned.

It is also in the aim of the project to benefit other partners in the consortium with less tradition of participating in SDOs and/or OS communities to work on joint contributions that could make them to become involved in these kinds of activities as a mean of increasing impact and outreach in the overall 6G ecosystem.

4.1 Standardization bodies of relevance for DESIRE6G

The overall standardization ecosystem in the telecom and IT industry is characterized by an extensive and diverse base of bodies, alliances and groups, provoking a very large fragmentation and making difficult the participation and influence for the majority of institutions involved. Only very large companies and organizations can guarantee a broad and continuous participation across all the SDO ecosystem.

The aforementioned fragmentation is motivated by several reasons. An obvious one is due to geographical reasons, with the existence of regional standardization bodies with the same or related scope. Other motivation for fragmentation of SDOs comes from the fact that some of those SDOs are chartered to address a subset of technologies or techniques, focussing on those areas of specialization. Furthermore, different industrial strategical interests originate in some cases the emergence of technically overlapped and technically competing approaches targeting the same problem space, producing situations of divergence across the industry. All of this makes difficult to influence and impact standards in general for the participating organizations, but also in particular from the RIA projects.

In order to overcome these limitations from DESIRE6G, the project is working on an internal exercise for identifying standardization bodies of interest and prioritization among them, since the fragmentation described before force a rationalization of the intended effort from the project. With that purpose, the primary step is to identify on one hand SDOs of interest and, on the other hand, SDOs where the project can maximize its impact. This will permit to concentrate the effort on the

SDOs in which the influence of the project can be higher, and establish complementary actions (e.g., collaboration with other projects and initiatives) in those other SDOs where the influence could be lower.

It is also important to note that as long as the project is executed, the areas of potential impact can vary. The main contributions will come from the architecture defined, the technical enablers and the development of the proposed innovations, and as such, with the evolution of the project (yet in its initial steps) the contributions beyond the state of the art will be more evident.

Moreover, it should be noted in which respect to 6G, that it can be expected as well an evolution of the SDOs themselves, with the emergence of new bodies, the declining of existing ones, or simply the evolution in scope of existing ones along the time.

A final aspect to consider is also the possible evolution in the interests of the institutions participating in the consortium with respect to target SDOs in line with their own exploitation plans, which can be also subject to change during the lifetime of the project.

In consequence, the set of bodies of interest for the project will require a periodic update consistent with the execution of the project, the alignment with the partners' interests, the evolution of the SDOs, and the overall development of 6G ecosystem.

The initial considerations stated in the project proposal for maximizing DESIRE6G impact on the standardization and industry forums were identified as follows:

- setup a standardization roadmap, to be updated regularly to be aligned with latest focus areas in the standardization arena in the definition of 6G;
- constant monitoring of and alignment to standardization activities that could bring value to the project, allowing to consider in the project execution phase the latest approaches as discussed by the industry;
- seize opportunities to push technology contributions into ongoing specifications or recommendations consequence of the innovations developed in the project; and
- promote continuously the project concept and solutions at standardization-related workshops, panels, and summits.

Regarding specific SDOs, DESIRE6G project is expected to yield enhancements and contributions for adding new technical capabilities with potentially significant impact on various relevant

standardization groups such as 3GPP, ETSI, ITU-T, IETF/IRTF, O-RAN, etc. The departing point became established in the Description of Action, according to Table 3.

TABLE 3: INITIAL STANDARDIZATION PLAN OF DESIRE6G

SDO	Partners	Expected impact
3GPP	ERI-HU, EBY, ACC, NVIDIA, TID	Architectural considerations for sharing telemetry information to external entities, e.g., DESIRE6G, as well as architecture enhancements for tactile and multimodality communications services. Exposure of DESIRE6G network and management capabilities through APIs in a controlled, secure, and auditable way. Architectural considerations for CU/DUs enabling telemetry interfaces serving DESIRE6G AI algorithms for traffic treatment
ETSI ZSM	TID	Contributions of DESIRE6G Zero-touch service management, multi-domain, and closed-loop automation.
O-RAN	ACC, TID	Contribution to Use Cases and Overall Architecture Workgroup and The Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) and E2 Interface Workgroup (O-RAN WG3), as well as contributions to the Xhaul transport solutions (O-RAN WG9).
IETF COINRG	UC3M, TID	Contributions on how the hyper-distributed edge can be applied for computing in the network.
IETF ICCRG	UC3M, ERI-HU, TID	Contributions to the implementation, standardization and performance of traffic management solutions for deep slicing.

Action on specific working groups needs to be defined as long as the project work on innovations start to ramp up. The foreseen contributions can lay on functional architectural work, specification of interfaces, and advanced protocol design. Specific actions will be detailed in future deliverables.

4.2 Open-Source communities of relevance for DESIRE6G

While standardization helps to define effective mechanisms to guarantee interoperability between distinct implementations, the open-source initiatives foster the validation of solutions in a fast and open way, allowing demonstration of feasibility and viability of technical approaches.

The network softwarization trend in the last decade has made evident the need of a very tight and efficient integration and reliance on software components of modern communication-oriented networks. Virtualization, programmability, learning and data processing are clear examples of such dependency. The expectation is that in 6G such as dependency will become even higher than in the past generations.

Similarly to the case before in regards the SDOs, there is a multiplicity of OS communities of relevance for the project. The purpose of the OS projects range from orchestration, management and control of a system up to the very specific programmability of the device's data plane. Different OS projects are subject to receiving contributions from DESIRE6G depending on the specific role they could play in the overall architecture, with the aim of validating the conceptual design.

It is also relevant to note that, in some cases, there is an intersection between SDOs and OS communities. For instance, this is what happens with ETSI Open-Source MANO (OSM) or ETSI TeraFlow SDN (TFS) projects. This results in a very effective way of validating proposed standard specifications while at the same time providing the proper feedback from an implementation standpoint.

As starting point for open-source activities, the Description of Action establishes some initial lines of action. For instance, it is foreseen to contribute with relevant communities such as Open Network Foundation-P4-Education WG and other initiatives such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, or ONOS. Once the DESIRE6G architecture becomes better structured and defined (end of Y1, early Y2), more clear usage of open source projects will be defined, and in consequence, it will become clearer the potential contributions from the project beyond current state-of-the-art functionalities available.

4.3 Project reach

In order to provide visibility and guidance on what can be the perimeter of the project at the initial stage, it was created an SDO matrix in order to understand what is the actual reach.

The following table shows the involvement declared by the partners in the consortium involved in standardization and open-source matters. The legend of the table is as follows:

- DC stands for Direct Contribution, which reflects the capability of actively contributing to some specific working group or OS project results coming from DESIRE6G, through participants in the project that can directly contribute to the corresponding SDO or OS community.
- IC that stands for Indirect Contribution, which reflects the capability of influencing contributions from DESIRE6G results through representatives from a consortium partner that can contribute to the corresponding SDO or OS community, but who are not participating directly in the project.
- M standing for Monitoring, which implies a follow up of the activities of the SDO and/or OS group, which can result in a potential capability of contributing results from DESIRE6G.

TABLE 4: INVOLVEMENT OF DESIRE6G PARTNERS IN STANDARDIZATION AND OPEN-SOURCE INITIATIVES

SDO Body	WG	Manufacturers				Oper.	SMEs			Academics							
		ERI-HU	EBY	NEC	NVIDIA	TID	ACC	NUBIS	TSS	UvA	UPC	UoU	UC3M	ELTE	CNIT	SSSA	
ETSI	NFV	M				DC						M					
	MEC	M										M					
	OSM	M				IC		M				M					
	ZSM	M	M			M	M										
	ENI	M															
ITU-T	TFS	M				DC										M	
	IMT-2030	M	M			M											
IETF	SG13					M											
	TEAS					DC						M					
	CCAMP					DC						M					
	DetNet	IC				M						DC					
	RAW	IC				M						DC					
	IPPM					M											
	MPLS					M											
	ALTO					DC							DC				
	CATS					DC							DC				
	PIM					DC											
	IRTF	NMRG	M				DC						DC	M			
		MAPRG											M				
COINRG		M				DC						DC	M				
ONF	TAPI					M									M		
	CORD																
ORAN	P4	M			M	M								IC	M		
	WG1	M	M					IC									
	WG2		M														
TIP	WG9	M				DC	IC										
	DCSG					DC											
	DDBR					DC											
IEEE	MUST					DC											
	802	IC										M					
TMForum			M														
3GPP	SA2	IC					M										
	SA5		IC			IC	M										
NGMN					M												
GSMA					M												
OCI	Spec							IC									
	containerd							IC									
OpenInfra	OpenStack							M					M				
	Kata-containers							DC									
ONOS													M	IC	M		
In-house open source							DC		DC	M	DC	DC		DC	DC		

Also in this case, due to the evolution of the SDOs and OS communities, as well as the changing interests of the companies in the consortium, but also to the proper technological evolution, a second round of the definition of this SDO and OS matrix can be expected. This will help on determining the

actual reach and better define how to impact the distinct SDOs/OS groups from the project for maximizing impact.

The project reach can be also described in terms of the direct interaction with SDOs and OS groups for the participation in standardization events, such as hackathons, plugfests, etc.

4.4 Topics for contribution

As the project execution will progress, it will become more evident what are the topics that could be subject of the previously mentioned bidirectional interaction with SDOs. The following lists collects some of the potential topics identified so far:

- Influence of standardization and open source in DESIRE6G (i.e., SDOs/OS communities → DESIRE6G)
 - 3GPP: support of Deterministic Networking (DetNet) capabilities in 3GPP architecture, initial analysis of 6G requirements and capabilities, etc.
 - TMForum and ETSI ZSM: zero touch service provision and lifecycle management.
 - IETF / IRTF: DetNet, mobility support, in-network and edge compute, technology-agnostic network slicing data models, etc.
 - O-RAN: smart control, slicing extended to CU/DU interfaces, etc.
 - Kubernetes: lightweight instantiation of functions and components.
 - P4: mechanisms for data plane programmability.
 - Graphana and Prometheus: means of exposing telemetry information.
- Influence of DESIRE6G in standardization and open source (i.e., DESIRE6G → SDOs/OS communities)
 - WP2: KPIs to be considered.
 - WP3: Definition of Intents, multi-domain orchestration.
 - WP4: Programmability of the data plane
 - WP5: Testing architecture and methodology

As long as the projects starts producing stable outcomes, including implementations showing feasibility, these and/or other topics are expected to generate contributions to standardization and open source.

4.5 Involvement on SNS JU activities related to standardization and open-source

At the time of writing this deliverable, the SNS JU is defining its structure in terms of working groups (see section 3.2 for more details), as it happened in the past with the 5G-PPP. Not having yet fully defined and scoped such working groups, from DESIRE6G there is the commitment to engage on those working groups relevant for the impact on standardization and/or open-source contributions.

Once those working groups become fully defined, the project will setup a strategy of participation and contribution from the project innovations and outcomes. Next deliverables will report the final form of participation in 6G-IA SNS working groups.

The participation in the working group(s) dealing with standardization and open-source is perceived from the project as strategical action since it permits the collaboration with other projects of the same phase, but also from future phases. This can permit a quick alignment of proposals and a fast development of the overall technologies surrounding the evolution towards 6G from a European dimension.

Linked also with this idea of collaboration, it is the aim of DESIRE6G to strength links with other projects, mainly from Stream-B, but also from the other streams, in order to join forces in the area of standardization and open-source so that the impact can be maximized. Initial steps in this direction have started, being yet soon to report any specific action in this direction.

5. Early achievements

5.1 Communication activities

In this section we report the early achievements in terms of communication since the project kick off on February 2nd of 2023 in Madrid.

5.1.1 Branding

At the kick off meeting, the project partners voted to choose the official logo of DESIRE6G designed by a professional graphic design company (Figure 2). Afterwards, a complete branding identity was created to ensure coherence and to be recognizable (see Figure 3). From that, templates were created in Word and PowerPoint for deliverables, reports, presentations and posters.

FIGURE 2: DESIRE6G'S MAIN LOGO AND HORIZONTAL LOGO

FIGURE 3: OFFICIAL COLOUR PALETTE AND FONTS FOR ALL DESIRE6G MATERIALS

5.1.2 Web, social media, and project communication material

POSTER

The first project poster (Figure 4) was presented at ETSI Research Conference (6th to 8th February 2023 in France) during the official presentation of the first phase of SNS JU projects. At that time, the design identity had not been finalized.

DESIRE6G - Deep Programmability & Secure Distributed Intelligence for Real-Time E2E 6G Networks

VISION
Design and develop a zero-touch control, management & orchestration platform, with native integration of AI, to support eXtreme URLLC application requirements over a performant, measurable and programmable data plane.

USE CASES

- ✓ Intelligent and resilient VR/AR applications with perceived zero latency (Italy)
- ✓ E2E Digital Twin (Spain)

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND KEY INNOVATIONS
 DESIRE6G will re-architect mobile networks targeting real time autonomic networking via:

1. A hybrid architecture employing lightweight centralized management & orchestration, with distributed intelligent control.
2. An E2E programmable user plane using a generic hardware abstraction layer, supporting heterogeneous systems e.g., GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs, SOCs.

 The system architecture will be complemented by a pervasive monitoring system to support the DESIRE6G data, control, management & orchestration plane. Distributed Ledger Technology will be used as a zero-trust mechanism.

Application
 State Policy Action
 E2E Service Management & Orchestration
 Service design tools
 MAS based Network Control
 UP-MS CP-MS
 Hardware Abstraction Layer
 Pervasive Monitoring

DESIRE6G Innovation

- Intelligent applications
- Intent-based orchestration
- Lightweight blockchain-based federation
- xURLLC services
- Serverless architecture
- RAN-core convergence
- Cloud-to-edge continuum
- Secure distributed intelligence
- E2E data plane programmability
- Multi HW acceleration
- E2E telemetry

DESIRE6G will employ distributed edge AI solutions to support energy & communication efficient model training and inference algorithm, considering application-level requirements, communication & compute resource constraints.

desire6g.eu
twitter.com/desire6g_eu
[linkedin.com/in/desire6g-project](https://www.linkedin.com/in/desire6g-project)
 Call Identifier: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022 STREAM-B-01-01
 Project Lifetime: 01/01/2023 - 31/12/2025
 Cost: €227,939k
 Project Coordinator: Dr. Chrysa Papagianni (University of Amsterdam)
 Technical Coordinator: Gergely Pongracz (Ericsson)

FIGURE 4: DESIRE6G PROJECT POSTER (FEBRUARY 2023)

BROCHURE

The project brochure was created to generate awareness about the project, as a simple and easy way to communicate the project's objectives and key innovations. The leaflet (shown in Figure 5) has been and will be displayed during events where DESIRE6G members participate as organizers or speakers

in workshops, panels, presentations, etc. Additionally, a QR code was added to the brochure to generate traffic to the project’s website.

Deep Programmability and Secure Distributed Intelligence for real-time E2E 6G Networks

PROJECT

Project coordinator:
Chrysa Papagianni, PhD
University of Amsterdam

Technical coordinator:
Gergely Pongracz, MSc
Ericsson Hungary

Duration:
01/01/2023- 31/12/2025

Cost:
6.227.919€

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 @DESIRE6G

VISION

Design and develop a zero-touch control, management & orchestration platform, with native integration of AI, to support verticals with extreme application requirements over a performant, measurable and programable data plane.

USE CASES

We focus on two representative 6G use cases targeting extreme key performance indicators:

- Digital Twin
- Intelligent and resilient VR/AR applications with perceived zero latency

KEY INNOVATIONS

DESIRE 6G will re-architect mobile networks targeting real time autonomic networking via:

1. A hybrid architecture employing lightweight centralized management & orchestration, with distributed intelligent control.
2. An E2E programmable user plane using a generic hardware abstraction layer, supporting heterogeneous systems e.g. GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs, SOCs.

The system architecture will be complemented by pervasive monitoring system will support the data, control, management & orchestration plane.

Distributed Ledger Technology will be used as a zero-trust mechanism.

DESIRE 6G will employ distributed, privacy preserving AI/ML approaches, while considering application-level requirements, communication, and compute resource constraints to support Edge Intelligence.

PARTNERS

FIGURE 5: PROJECT BROCHURE (MAY 2023)

WEBSITE

The project website <https://desire6g.eu/> was created at the beginning of the project and launched to the public on March 30th. Figure 6 shows the landing page.

FIGURE 6: DESIRE6G WEBSITE LANDING PAGE

The initial statistics from the project website have been collected and will be used to monitor engagement throughout the project's lifetime (data retrieved as of June 19th 2023).

TABLE 5: WEBSITE TOTAL VISITS

All Time Values 30 th March – 19 th June	#
Total visits	1601
Total visitors	788

The distribution of visits and visitors shows that there is an increased activity coinciding with posts about events, where many people and institutions are tagged.

FIGURE 7: CHART OF DESIRE6G.EU VISITS AND VISITORS SINCE MAY 1ST (NOT EARLIER DATA AVAILABLE).

TABLE 6: MOST VISITED PAGES AND TOTAL VIEWS ON DESIRE6G.EU AS OF JUNE 19TH

#	Page title	Total visits
1	Home Page	955
2	Project	88
3	Consortium	77
4	Publications	57
5	Deliverables	53
6	Vision	44
7	Executive team	39
8	Workshop 6G-PDN	34
9	Dissemination and Exploitation	33
10	Contact	29

SOCIAL MEDIA

DESIRE6G has been active on social media via LinkedIn and Twitter, mostly informing about upcoming events, new publications, but also engaging with the research community around topics like 6G, network security and efficiency, programmability and machine learning. Additionally, a conscious effort was done to share content and activities relatable to a broader audience, such as science communication, education, collaborative research and women in STEM.

Below are shown the aggregated statistics from DESIRE6G’s social media accounts. From Table 7 and Table 9 we can extract that LinkedIn has been a more successful network for DESIRE6G’s outreach

efforts (153 vs 42 followers). One explanation is that DESIRE6G members and their colleagues and peers are more active on LinkedIn, which is truly used as a professional social network. On the other hand, very few members have an account on Twitter, which results in less interaction.

LinkedIn Analytics

TABLE 7: ANALYTICS OF @DESIRE6G.EU LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS, VISITORS AND ENGAGEMENT. FEBRUARY TO JUNE 2023

	Total values	Last 30 days
Followers	153	21 new followers
Visitors		
Page views	354	68
Unique visitors	174	30
Custom button clicks	30	2
Content		
Reactions	364	124
Comments	7	0
Reposts	31	8

TABLE 8: LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS DEMOGRAPHICS BY LOCATION ON JUNE 20TH 2023

Metropolitan city Area	Numbers of followers	Percentage of total
Madrid Area, Spain	36	25.5%
Budapest, Hungary	7	5%
Barcelona, Spain	6	4.3%
The Randstad, Netherlands,	5	3.5%
Pisa, Italy	4	2.8%
Brussels, Belgium	4	2.8%
Greater Istanbul, Turkey	3	2.1%
Athens, Greece	3	2.1%
João Pessoa, Brazil	2	1.4%
Paris, France	2	1.4%

Twitter statistics

TABLE 9: ANALYTICS ON @DESIRE6G FOLLOWERS AND ACTIVITY DATA FROM FEBRUARY 7TH TO JUNE 20TH 2023

	Total values	Last month
Followers	42	12
Following	52	10
Activity		
Tweets	72	1
Tweet impressions	2,400	1,111
Profile visits	3,275	31
Mentions	21	2

The current statistics are in the middle range compared with similar Horizon Europe projects and serve as our starting point for the future reports (D6.3 and D6.5). Additionally, the first months of communication activities through the website, LinkedIn and Twitter have been very useful to identify the strategy and kind of posts that generate most engagement. A highlight has been the continuous and regular increase of visitors, indicating that our efforts and improvements drive positive results.

Interaction in social media

The individual members' participation and activity on social media has been crucial to achieve the online presence of DESIRE6G. Through following, sharing, liking, and reposting from their own personal accounts, DESIRE6G's posts gained significant popularity. Moreover, interaction with other SNS JU projects (mainly PREDICT6G and DETERMINISTIC6G) and official accounts of organizations (such as SNS JU, 6G Flagship, and EuCNC2023) generated a lot of additional views.

5.1.3 Communication Talks and other actions

PRESS RELEASE

An initial news piece was published by the University of Amsterdam, containing an interview to the project coordinator Dr. Chrysa Papagianni, accessible here:

<https://ivi.uva.nl/content/news/2023/03/uva-led-european-project-aims-to-lay-foundations-for-6g-network-architecture.html>

The release was further disseminated to news outlets in the BENELUX:

<https://www.emerce.nl/wire/door-uva-geleid-europees-project-legt-basis-6gnetwerkarchitectuur>

<https://engineeringnet.be/nl/nieuws/item/21278>

Secondly, a public press release was released in June 2023, which was shared on the project website, announced through social media and by the partners' own channels and networks. The press release can be read here: <https://desire6g.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation/press-release/>

COMMUNICATION TALKS AND OTHER ACTIONS

Beyond the official communication activities by Task 6.1 (lead by UVA), all partners contributed to raising awareness of the project during the first 6 months. Table 10 below showcases the great diversity of communication actions carried out by the project partners, in line with their sector and possibilities.

TABLE 10: COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES ABOUT DESIRE6G

Communication action	Partner
Internal university newsletter about the project an interview with Project coordinator	UVA
Project presentation at JU SNS Lunch Webinar	UVA
Science Fair in Madrid and news item on university website	UC3M
Project Coordinator video at EuCNC2023, accessible at 6G SNS YouTube channel	UVA
DESIRE6G presentation in the lecture about Cellular Networks (part of Advanced Networking Masters Course)	UVA
LinkedIn promotion of published open access scientific articles	CNIT
DESIRE6G presentation during Ericsson Open House Day	ERI-HU
DESIRE6G presentation to Hungarian authorities within Ericsson's R&D portfolio	ERI-HU
Articles on university and faculty website and newsletter	ELTE
Marketing activities achieved featuring in 14 national ICT/ business digital portals	ELTE
Internal and external Ericsson Research Türkiye newsletters	EBY
Project presentation and news for the Turkish Research Council	EBY
DESIRE6G presentations for Turk Telekom Innovation Directorate & Turkcell Academy	EBY
DESIRE6G project presentation in the lecture about Algorithmic Methods for Mathematical Models (part of Master in Innovation and Research in Informatics)	UPC
LinkedIn promotion of the project, publications, events and collaboration between partners	NVIDIA
Project explanation in the company's website	TSS
Project presentation during 5G/6G Seasonal School	SSSA

5.2 Dissemination activities

In this section we report the dissemination activities of the project. DESIRE6G has carried out multiple dissemination activities, even if the project is still at its early stage, this included presentations in multiple conferences, seminars and forums.

5.2.1 Publications and technical dissemination

Table 11 presents DESIRE6G peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals and studies/demos/posters in scientific conferences. Item titles contain links to the articles in Zenodo. Only published or accepted publications are shown.

TABLE 11: DESIRE6G PUBLICATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS AND CONFERENCES (CONF.).

Type	Title	Publication/Conference	Publication date
journal	DESIRE6G: Deep Programmability & Secure Distributed Intelligence for Real-Time E2E 6G Networks	European 6G Annual Journal	06/06/2023
journal	P4 Telemetry collector	Computer Networks	23/03/2023
journal	P4-assisted seamless migration of serverless applications towards the edge continuum	Future Generation Computer Systems	28/04/2023
journal	Deep Learning-Based Adaptive Compression and Anomaly Detection for Smart B5G Use Cases Operation	Sensors	16/01/2023
conf.	Dynamic Traffic Prediction Model Retraining for Autonomous Network Operation	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2023)	03/05/2023
conf..	Pervasive Monitoring and Distributed Intelligence for 6G Near Real-Time Operation	European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC23)	18/04/2023
conf.	V2N Service Scaling with Deep Reinforcement Learning	IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium	01/02/2023
conf.	Comparison of Statistical and Machine Learning-Based Approaches for Telemetry Data Size Reduction	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2023)	03/05/2023
conf.	Securing Multi-Agent Systems for Near Real-Time Control of 6G Services	European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC23)	03/05/2023

Table 12 presents DESIRE6G consortium talks at scientific conferences, seminars and forums, with the goal to raise awareness on the DESIRE6G project. An example of a talk at EuCNC is shown in Figure 8.

TABLE 12: DESIRE6G TALKS IN SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES AND TECHNOLOGY FORA

Date	Venue	Description
19-20 September 2022	Medipol University, Istanbul, Turkey	Ericsson Turkey's project presentation of DESIRE6G in 6G Conference
8-11 May 2023	University of Coimbra, Portugal	Optical Network Design and Modelling #ONDM2023 Workshop: Challenges of Optical Communications in the 6G era
22-26 May 2023	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy	ARTIST - 5G/6G networks trAnsfoRming The dlgital SocieTy Seasonal School featured lectures and lab sessions stemming from DESIRE6G work
6 June 2023	EuCNC 2023, Gothenburg	DESIRE6G - Employing deep programmability and distributed intelligence for real-time 6G networks - Chrysa Papagianni
6 June 2023	EuCNC 2023, Gothenburg	DESIRE6G - "End-to-end data plane abstraction for supporting deep slicing in 6G"- Sandor Laki

FIGURE 8: DR. CHRYSA PAPAGIANNI AT EUCNC 2023

5.2.2 Synergies with other projects

The following table reports collaborative activities with other EU and international research projects towards a coordinated action inside the SNS JU.

TABLE 13: COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES WITH EU AND INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH PROJECTS

Date	Item	Explanation
9 June 2023	Future deterministic programmable networks for 6G Workshop	Organization of the workshop where determinism was discussed together with PREDICT-6G, DETERMINISTIC6G at EuCNC2023
10 May 2023	Challenges of optical communications in the 6G era Workshop	Organization of the workshop where 6 EU projects discuss their approaches to optical communications in 6G at ONDM 2023
23 October 2023	6G-PDN (6G Programmable Deterministic Networking with AI) Workshop	Organization ongoing jointly by DESIRE6G and PREDICT-6G at MobiHoc 2023
24 March 2023	Inteligencia Artificial en el control remoto de un brazo robótico.	Joint scientific dissemination activity targeting high school students. Collaboration of DESIRE6G, PREDICT-6G, Hexa-X-II, 6G-EDGEDT and 6G-DATADRIVEN

5.2.3 Bachelor, Master, PhD Theses, and Internships

The following table reports bachelor, master and PhD theses as well as internships on matters related to DESIRE6G.

TABLE 14: DESIRE6G-RELATED BACHELOR, MASTER AND PHD THESES, AND INTERNSHIPS

Type (PhD/Master/Int.)	Partner	State (Ongoing /Finished)	Title
PhD	UC3M	Ongoing	Enhanced, time sensitive, reliable and available wireless networks based on AI
PhD	UC3M	Ongoing	Development of reliable SDN-based wireless and virtualization technologies for real-time scenarios

BSc	UVA	Ongoing	Jan Laan, “Extending a simulation framework for virtualised infrastructures”
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5.3 Standardization and Open Source

The target for the DESIRE6G project is 10 contributions to SDOs, such as 3GPP, IETF, ETSI, IEEE, O-RAN, ITU over the lifetime of the project. Table 15 summarizes current SDO activities and candidate contributions:

TABLE 15: CURRENT SDO ACTIVITIES AND CANDIDATE CONTRIBUTIONS

SDO	Type of Document (Contribution / Dissemination)	DESIRE6G partner	Link to Candidate contribution
IETF (DetNet WG)	Contribution	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-detnet-controller-plane-framework/04
IETF (DetNet WG)	Contribution	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-bernardos-detnet-multidomain/01
O-RAN (WG9)	Contribution on DetNet overview as discussion input for the Xhaul packet switching specification	TID	https://oranalliance.atlassian.net/wiki/pages/viewpageattachments.action?pageId=2653487497&preview=%2F2653487497%2F2774335856%2FTEF-2023.02.06-WG9-XPAAS-DetNet-v0.pptx&search_id=9e0b9630-e3fa-435e-bcfb-6df1c7a37452
3GP (SA5)	Contribution to improve EP_Transport model of TS 28.541 in Release 18 to clarify connection point for network slicing when interworking with transport networks	TID	https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/tsg_sa/WG5_TM/TSGS5_149/Docs/S5-234742.zip

Regarding Open Source contributions, at the time of writing this deliverable it is still too early to have contributions (focus is on the architecture and specification work). The plan is to make some pieces of the DESIRE6G stack available as open source in the project Github repository: <https://github.com/DESIRE6G>.

6. References

[1] DESIRE6G, «D1.1: Data Management Plan» 2023.